

Two-phase coexistence in a model membrane observed by natural abundance ^1H - ^{13}C solid-state NMR

Lucas Löser, Kay Saalwächter, and Tiago Mendes Ferreira
NMR - Institute for Physics, Martin-Luther University Halle-Wittenberg
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We demonstrate that ^1H - ^{13}C solid-state NMR is suitable to detect liquid disordered / liquid ordered phase coexistence in a ternary lipid mixture with natural abundance of isotopes as alternative to ^2H NMR. Such methodology is potentially applicable to study lipid phase coexistence phenomena in biological matter with high lipid content, e.g. lung surfactant or myelin, for which isotopic labeling is not possible.

I. INTRODUCTION

From 1970 until present, there has been a gradual shift from the fluid-mosaic model by Singer and Nicholson [1], which assumes that lipid bilayers in cells act as a passive homogeneous two-dimensional fluid, towards a more complex picture where lipid bilayer heterogeneities also play an important role in cellular processes. In this context, two independent developments had a significant impact on the change of paradigm.

One was the emergence of the *lipid raft* concept by Simons and coworkers whom have postulated the existence of small sphingolipid-cholesterol domains in lipid bilayers that can sort membrane proteins and affect their function [2–5]. This conceptual idea was mostly based on contributions from membrane protein solubilization studies, namely the analysis of detergent-resistant membrane fractions yielding high concentrations on sphingolipids, cholesterol, and the postulated *lipid raft* proteins [6–8]. An accurate definition of *lipid rafts* has been a difficult task due to their elusive character. At present however, there is compelling evidence from different imaging techniques that various types of *lipid rafts* exist with respect to size and functionality [9, 10]. Being undeniably powerful, such images of lipid domains need to be interpreted with care since they rely on fluorescent probes which may affect the system under observation [11–14]. Nevertheless, at present, it is widely accepted that biological membranes contain liquid lipid heterogeneities in contrast to the homogeneous fluid initially assumed in the fluid-mosaic model.

The other important development has been the progress in the structural characterization of ternary lipid mixtures [15] with a variety of experimental methods such as nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) [16, 17], electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) [18, 19], atomic force microscopy [20], scattering techniques [21, 22] and fluorescence microscopy [23], as well as with theoretical methods e.g. molecular dynamics simulations [24]. All of these different techniques have been used to show that in various ternary lipid systems containing cholesterol, it is possible to observe lateral phase heterogeneity including a liquid disordered / liquid ordered (l_d/l_o) phase coexistence where domain sizes range from a few nm to μm depending on the composition of the system.

To what extent the heterogeneous behavior observed in ternary systems is relevant in biological membranes which have a much higher number of components and are not in thermodynamic equilibrium is not straightforward, as it is not clear if there is a relation between the phenomena observed in the lipid models with the *lipid raft* concept [25, 26]. From model systems it has been suggested that the line tension between coexistent liquid phase domains determines domain size [27, 28]. As line tension approaches zero, domain sizes fluctuate and the system reaches a critical point [16, 29]. Moreover, it has also been observed in model systems that some biological molecules have line activity in heterogeneous lipid bilayers analogously to surfactants in emulsions [30]. One fundamental open question is if cells make use of such properties for cellular mechanisms i.e. if the cell controls the lipid composition or the concentration of some *line-actants* in the bilayer as means to control domain sizes and therefore lateral organization in the membrane. In this context, it has been recently suggested that the anesthetic effect of n-alcohols may be related to their effect on the critical temperature of biological lipid bilayers [31].

To investigate the potential connection between simple models and pure biological systems, the same experiments done on the model systems should be applicable to the biological systems which poses a complication since the techniques referred to above require the inclusion of probe molecules, isotopic labeling, or some special kind of sample preparation protocol, making them unpractical for studying pure biological samples.

Concerning the detection of two-phase and three-phase coexistence in ternary lipid mixtures, four main techniques have been used successfully so far, ^2H NMR [11, 16, 17], fluorescence microscopy [32, 33], EPR [18, 19] and X-ray scattering [21, 34], however none of these techniques is currently suitable to measure whole biological samples without insertion of probe molecules or without unidirectional orientation of the bilayers which involves destruction of the biological sample of interest for subsequent reconstitution. Fluorescence microscopy techniques are very important since they enable to observe biological membranes using residual quantities of fluorescent probes in living cells [35] and progress has been done in order to find non-perturbing probes [12]. Regardless the effects of probe molecules on the system under

FIG. 1. The isothermal plane of the DPPC/DOPC/cholesterol ternary mixture at 24 °C as determined by Juhasz et al. [37]. The samples investigated are represented in the diagram. The boundaries shown in gray enclose the two-phase coexistence regions (A) l_d (L_α disordered) + l_o (L_α ordered), (B) l_d + S_o , (C) l_o + S_o and the three-phase region (III) l_d + l_o + S_o . L_α and S_o denote lamellar phases with liquid and gel-like properties, respectively.

investigation, probe insertion may be difficult to implement on samples of interest with higher complexity, e.g. white matter, where membrane heterogeneities are expected from studies on model systems [36] and complementary methods are needed.

In this communication we demonstrate that it is possible to use ^1H - ^{13}C dipolar recoupling NMR, namely R-PDLF spectroscopy [38], to measure l_d/l_o phase coexistence from a DPPC/DOPC/cholesterol ternary mixture, one of the most well known model membrane systems, using samples with natural abundance of isotopes. The technique has been applied recently to a clinical grade lung surfactant (extracted from porcine lung surfactant with organic solvents) where a gel/liquid phase coexistence was observed but no l_d/l_o coexistence [39]. Here we demonstrate that the liquid-liquid phase coexistence is also accessible by ^1H - ^{13}C dipolar recoupling NMR as for ^2H NMR and that therefore such methodology can be used to investigate l_d/l_o phase coexistence in non-manipulated biological samples with high lipid-membrane content e.g. lung surfactant or white matter.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We have prepared a number of hydrated DPPC/DOPC/cholesterol mixtures with distinct compositions as described in the Electronic Supplementary Information (ESI). The samples studied are represented in the Gibbs triangle shown in Figure 1 together with the phase diagram determined by Davis and coworkers by fluorescence microscopy and ^2H NMR [37].

According to the phase diagram shown, all the samples prepared consist of a coexistence of two distinct liquid phases, a liquid ordered and a liquid disordered phase, except the DPPC/DOPC/cholesterol sample with composition 31:58:11 (mol%) which should consist of an homogeneous liquid disordered phase. Our aim is to investigate if the l_d/l_o coexistence may be observed by ^1H - ^{13}C NMR using samples with no ^2H isotopic labeling and without using any fluorescent probe molecules. The difference of phase behavior between the DPPCd62/DOPC/cholesterol system studied by Davis and coworkers [17, 37] to the DPPC/DOPC/cholesterol system studied here should not be significant, however since the intermediate regime time-scales for ^2H quadrupolar couplings and ^1H - ^{13}C dipolar couplings are different by approximately one order of magnitude, it is possible that samples which show coexistence in ^2H NMR spectra can give rise to averaged dipolar recoupled spectra depending on the domain average size.

Figure 2A shows the ^{13}C direct polarization spectra of samples with DPPC/DOPC/cholesterol compositions equal to 31:58:11 and 48:34:18 (black triangle and blue square in Fig. 1, respectively). The 1D ^{13}C NMR spectra are normalized by making the areas of the γ peak at approximately 54 ppm to be relative to each other (the full spectrum is given as ESI). The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of sample 48:34:18 (blue line) contains all the chemical shift resonances observed in the spectrum of sample 31:58:11 (black line) plus a few additional peaks. The most pronounced difference between the two spectra is the appearance of a very broad peak at around 31 ppm for sample 48:34:18. If such spectral feature is an exclusive signature of the liquid ordered phase, the procedure of spectral subtraction used by Davis and coworkers [17] can be extended to ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy at natural abundance using ^{13}C direct polarization (DP) NMR spectra instead of ^2H quadrupolar spectra, i.e. for systems exhibiting such signature, the simple measurement of ^{13}C spectra for two distinct samples lying on a tie line would be sufficient to calculate its end points. However, from inspection of the 1D spectra alone, it is difficult to determine which peaks in the spectrum consist of pure phases and which result from averaging of the l_d and l_o spectra, and therefore if such additional feature in the spectrum could be used in a quantitative way.

Figure 2B shows the R-PDLF spectra of these samples. The dipolar splittings of the spectral components in both samples are equal for peaks that overlap at the same chemical shift (shown as ESI). On the other hand, the dipolar splittings for the extra components at 22.9, 25.5 and 31-32 ppm are larger than for their close neighbouring peaks at 22.6, 25 and 30.5-31 ppm, respectively. The R-PDLF spectrum of a third sample with composition 39:40:21 is also shown on the bottom of Figure 2B. We shall now demonstrate that this spectrum features a crowded spectral region that results from l_d/l_o averaging and that the spectrum of sample 48:34:18 displays a l_d/l_o superposition.

FIG. 2. ^1H - ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy of DPPC/DOPC/cholesterol samples with the compositions 31:58:11 (black) and 48:34:18 (blue). (A) ^{13}C direct polarization NMR spectra after acquisition of 1024 transients with a recycle delay of 5 s. (B) Regions of the ^1H - ^{13}C R-PDLF spectrum for the two samples with labels to identify DOPC and DPPC carbon segments. All spectra were acquired using a MAS frequency of 5.15 kHz and SPINAL64 decoupling at an RF frequency of 50 KHz.

Figure 3 shows the dipolar slices for the samples 31:58:11 and 48:34:18 at 30.8 and 32.2 ppm clearly showing an additional splitting at 32.2 ppm for sample 48:34:18. This dipolar splitting corresponds to a C-H bond order parameter of 0.43, as measured with an R-PDLF experiment using CP as polarization transfer to boost the signal for the highest couplings, and corresponds to the maximum order parameter measured from DPPCd62 in the l_o phase with ^2H NMR [17]. The maximum C-H bond order parameter of the l_d phase is also known from the previous ^2H NMR work by Davis and coworkers [17] and is equal to 0.27 which is the same as calculated from the dipolar splitting at 30.8 ppm for samples 31:58:11 and 48:34:18 (also for sample 54:25:21 which gives essentially the same results as sample 48:34:18 as shown in the ESI). This proves that the extra spectral component in the ^{13}C spectrum of sample 48:34:18 is in-

deed a signature of the l_o phase and that it is therefore possible to observe phase coexistence with ^{13}C solid-state NMR spectroscopy as in ^2H NMR despite the difference of time-scales between the two methods. However, this depends on the composition of the samples. For sample 39:40:21 we could not observe such superposition but instead a dipolar splitting at 31 ppm that is a result from averaging between the l_d/l_o phases.

We believe that the findings here shown will motivate and be used as reference for dipolar recoupling NMR studies on more complex samples, specially biological samples, for which isotopic labeling is not possible.

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FIG. 3. R-PDLF dipolar slices showing the maximum acyl chain ^1H - ^{13}C dipolar splittings for the liquid disordered (top) and liquid ordered (bottom) phases. The higher middle peak from the R-PDLF CP experiment is due to the surrounding non-covalently bound protons.

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